

Hybrid Hierarchical Clustering Approach for Community Detection in Social Network

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Abstract—Social Networks generally present a hierarchy of communities. To determine these communities and the relationship between them, detection algorithms should be applied. Most of the existing algorithms, proposed for hierarchical communities identification, are based on either agglomerative clustering or divisive clustering. In this paper, we present a hybrid hierarchical clustering approach for community detection based on both bottom-up and bottom-down clustering. Obviously, our approach provides more relevant community structure than hierarchical method which considers only divisive or agglomerative clustering to identify communities. Moreover, we performed some comparative experiments to enhance the quality of the clustering results and to show the effectiveness of our algorithm.

Keywords—Social network, community structure, opinion mining, agglomerative hierarchical clustering, divisive hierarchical clustering, hybrid hierarchical clustering.

I. INTRODUCTION AND RELATED WORK

THE rapid widespread of social networks has enabled large numbers of users to communicate, create and share content as well as give and receive recommendations. This rapid widespread has led to the emergence of new research area called Social Networks Analysis (SNA) which focuses on measuring and mapping the relationships and transitions between social networks users [13]. Therefore, social network analysis is based primarily on graph theory and sociological analysis. While communities structure in social networks is based on common interests, topics, hobbies, etc. [15], detected communities, in our work, rely on common sentiment. Due to the growing availability of opinions in social network, it becomes important to deal with mining these opinions and know what other people think in various fields as economics, politics, etc. [14], [18], [20]. In the literature there are several techniques of sentiment analysis as machine learning. Pang et al. [16] were the first who applied supervised learning methods (naïve Bayes classification, and support vector machines (SVM)) to classify movie reviews into two classes, positive and negative. Besides, machine learning has been also used by many authors in order to extract opinions from social networks [17], [19]. In [11] authors describe an optimal sentiment analysis method based on metaheuristic and SVM to extract positive, negative and fuzzy opinion. Moreover, as we try to construct the user communities based on the common opinions, we will review some studies relying on the hierarchical structure of

networks. Indeed, an interesting property of social networks is that they often exhibit a hierarchical structure with smaller communities dwelling inside larger communities. Thus, several hierarchical community detection methods in social networks were proposed [4], [10], [12]. These approaches can be classified into two major categories: divisive techniques and agglomerative ones. Indeed, hierarchical clustering may be constructed by either bottom-up approach, which successively joins the nearest point and group of points, or by top-down technique, which successively divides groups of points into sub-groups. The most well-known divisive algorithm is the algorithm of Girvan and Newman [1]. Therefore, the betweenness of an edge in an undirected graph designates the number of the shortest paths between pairs of nodes running through this edge. Besides, the idea behind this method is to remove edge with the highest betweenness centrality and to recalculate for each iteration this value [3]. But, as indicated in [2], [4], the used algorithm makes heavy demands on computational resources, running in $O(m^2n)$ time on an arbitrary network with m edges and n vertices, or $O(n^3)$ time on a sparse graph. To avoid this weakness, several algorithms [5], [7] proposed measures based on quickly-calculated betweenness centrality. However, these approaches failed to overcome the slowdown of the betweenness process. Besides, modularity based methods are efficient hierarchical clustering algorithms for community detection in social networks. In fact, the modularity of a graph with respect to some division (or vertex types) measures how good the division is, or how the different vertex types are separated from each other. Newman [3], [6] introduced the first greedy method to maximize modularity. His technique presents a hierarchical clustering way where edges are not contained in the graph initially. In fact, edges are added one by one during the hierarchical procedure. Additionally, the complexity of the different proposed agglomerative hierarchical clustering algorithms is at least $O(n^3)$. Indeed, various approaches focused on how to find the two most similar communities:

- the single linkage clustering method: This technique selects, at each iteration, the two communities having the smallest element of the similarity matrix X , such that vertex i is in one community and vertex j is in the other community.
- The complete link hierarchy method: its procedure is almost the opposite of the single linkage clustering method. Hence, at each iteration, this method selects the maximum element of X and merges the communities of vertices i and j . Sibson presented an algorithm for constructing the single linkage hierarchy. Then, Defays

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extended Sibson's approach to give a complete link hierarchy [8].

- The average linkage clustering method: The principle of such method consists in computing the average of all similarity values [8].

Indeed, the hierarchical community detection algorithms have a number of drawbacks. Namely, as noted in [4], [9], these approaches make heavy demands on computational resources. Hence, although bottom-up clustering is good at identifying small communities, it can provide sub-optimal performance to identify few large communities. Conversely, top-down methods are good at identifying a few large communities, but they are not efficiently used to detect many small communities. Consequently, the main disadvantage of this approach is that many partitions are recovered. In this case we cannot define the best division. In this paper, we seek to combine the strengths of both approaches modifying top-down procedure with information gained from a preliminary bottom-up clustering.

II. PROPOSAL

In this section, we define and formalize our idea.

A. Problem Formulation

Social network can be modeled by a graph $G = (V, E, \omega)$, where V represents the users in the network, E denotes the different interactions between them and $\omega_{i,j}$ is the edge label between two nodes (i, j) . In fact, $\omega_{i,j}$ = Similarity (i, j) . Thus, to each node, we associate opinions of the social network members determined by using supervised machine learning method proposed in [11]. Then, we weight each edge by the value of Jaccard Similarity defined in (1). In fact, the coefficient of Jaccard [21] is an index of the set neighbors intersection, obtained without applying any semantic analysis of their meaning. It represents the ratio between the cardinal (size) of the intersection of the considered sets and the Cardinal of the union of sets. It also measures the similarity between these two sets. In our case, the basic idea of computing similarity is: Given two opinions sets Op_i and Op_j (Op_i represents opinions of user (V_i) while Op_j denotes opinions of user (V_j)), we use the coefficient of jaccard to measure the semantic and the structural similarity where we replace Op_i by N_i representing the neighbor node of user (V_i) and Op_j by N_j denoting the neighbor node of user (V_j) . In fact, we define the index for determining the semantic similarity as:

$$JS(Op_i, Op_j) = \frac{Op_i \cap Op_j}{Op_i \cup Op_j} \quad (1)$$

B. Hybrid Community Detection Method

In the rest of the paper, we will employ the notations presented in Table I: The proposed hybrid hierarchical community detection approach is a successful heuristic based on the combination of different hierarchical methods used to find clusters in complex networks. The first technique is the

TABLE I
 USEFUL NOTATION

$G(V,E,\omega)$	undirected and weighted graph
U	Set of social networks Users $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$
c	Set of sub-detected groups constituting a community C
C	Detected Community
C	$C = \underbrace{\{\{u_1, u_2\}\}}_{c_1} + \dots + \underbrace{\{\{u_{100}, u_n\}\}}_{c_m}$
n	number of nodes (V)
m	number of sub-detected groups
k	level partition
K	number of partitions at level k
JSS	Jaccard Semantic Similarity value

ascendant algorithm (R1) relying on the aggregation operator. In fact, at each iteration, R1 merges the two communities having the highest JSS . However, the second method (R2) is a descendant hierarchical clustering algorithm based on removing edges having less JSS . Finally, the third technique is the hybrid algorithm which combines R1 and R2. In fact, it assumes the existence of an initial solution originally composed of m partitions (groups). It does not change the number of partitions, but it modifies the initial distribution.

The hybrid algorithm proceeds by successive combinations of the two operators R1 and R2. The aggregation operator provides a partition of $(m - 1)$ groups on which it is sufficient to apply the decomposition operator to get back the initial number of groups (m). The algorithm ends when a fixed partition is obtained. Hence, the successive combination of the aggregation and the decomposition operators leads to the appearance of the introduced hybrid hierarchical clustering community detection (HHCCD) algorithm based on the combination of agglomerative and divisive algorithms.

1. Agglomerative or Ascendant Algorithm R1 Based on an Aggregation Principle

We summarize the steps of this iterative algorithm in these primordial stages:

- 1) At the beginning, each vertex represents a separate community.
- 2) It initially considers that each social network user constitutes a community: $C = \{\{u_1\}, \{u_2\}, \dots, \{u_n\}\}$
- 3) At each iteration, the algorithm moves from one level k to the next by performing an aggregation procedure which consists in clustering two users, having the highest similarity measure, in the same community.
- 4) The algorithm ends up if all users are clustered in the same community and the aggregation procedure is no longer feasible.

Therefore, for a given level k , the algorithm R1 examines all pairs of groups constituting the community C_k to find the two groups c_α and c_β having the highest JSS value. Hence, the pseudo-code of the ascendant algorithm is given in Table II.

2. Divisive or Descendant Algorithm R2 Based on a Decomposition Principle

The decomposition algorithm (R2) is similar to the previously-described one. However, it is preceded by an opposite hierarchical construction. Contrary to R1, the

TABLE II
 PSEUDO-CODE OF ASCENDANT ALGORITHM R1

Require: input: graph G(V,E)
Ensure: output: k sub-detected communities

- 1: $K := n - 1$
- 2: **repeat**
- 3: $C_k = C_k \setminus \{c_\alpha, c_\beta\} \cup \{c_\alpha \cup c_\beta\}$ such that.
 $JSS(c_\alpha, c_\beta) = \max(JSS_{i,j}(u_i, u_j))$.
 $JSS(R1(C_k)) := JSS(C_k - JSS(c_\alpha, c_\beta))$ $k := k - 1$
- 4: **until** $K=2$

TABLE III
 PSEUDO-CODE OF DESCENDANT ALGORITHM R2

Require: input: graph G(V,E)
Ensure: output: k sub-detected communities

- 1: $K := 1$
- 2: **repeat**
- 3: $C_k = C_k \setminus c_k \cup c_k \setminus u^*, u^*$ Such that.
 $JSS(c_\alpha \setminus u^*, u^*) ; JSS(c_\alpha \setminus u, u) \forall c_\alpha \in C_k, \forall y \subset c_\alpha$.
 $JJS(R2(C_k)) = JJS(C_k + JJS(c_\alpha \setminus u^*, u^*))$ $k = k + 1$
- 4: **until** $K=n-1$

TABLE IV
 PSEUDO-CODE OF HHCCDA

Require: input: graph G(V,E)
Ensure: output: k detected communities

- 1: $k := 1$
- 2: **repeat**
- 3: **repeat**
- 4: $C_k = R1oR2(C_k)$.
- 5: **until** $(R1oR2(C_k))=C_k$
- 6: **repeat**
- 7: $C_k = R2oR1(C_k)$.
- 8: **until** $(R2oR1(C_k))=C_k$
- 9: **until** $(R1oR2(C_k))=(R2oR1(C_k))=C_k$

proposed descendant algorithm follows these fundamental steps:

- 1) Algorithm R2 initially considers that all social network users constitute a community. In fact, the algorithm begins with a partition containing a single community: $C = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n\}$
- 2) At each iteration, R2 moves from one level k to the next by performing a decomposition procedure: successive separations into two partitions generating the least important similarity value.
- 3) The algorithm stops if the bursting procedure is no longer feasible.

Therefore, in Table III, we described the pseudo-code of the proposed descendant algorithm.

Therefore, at each level K , algorithm R2 examines the division of all pairs of groups c_α and c_β constituting the community C_k to find the two groups $c_{\alpha'}$ and $c_{\beta'}$ having the least JSS value. Indeed, for each c_α we must examine all partitions as $c_\alpha \setminus u, u$, with $u \subseteq c_\alpha$ and $u \neq \emptyset$.

3. Hybrid Hierarchical Algorithm

The hybrid or mixed algorithm exploits alternatively the two previously-mentioned algorithms. Indeed, *HHCCD* can be summarized in these steps:

- 1) The *HHCCD* requires the existence of an initial solution of k community.
- 2) It proceeds by a successive combination of the ascendant and descendant algorithms. In fact, the decomposition operator provides a partition of $(k - 1)$ groups on which it is sufficient to apply the aggregation operator to obtain the number of the initial group (K) and vice versa. At this point, we prove that partition into k groups is better than the previous one.

- 3) The algorithm stops if the obtained result remains constant (stable solution obtained through the application of either the aggregation or decomposition operator).

Consequently, referring to the process of stabilization, we should apply R1oR2 or R2oR1 in a regular order. Hence, we use the aggregation operator (R1oR2) until obtaining the same detected community. In the same way, we apply the decomposition operator (R2oR1) until getting fixed detected groups (see Table IV).

C. Running Example of HHCCD

We consider the graph presented in Fig. 1 composed of six nodes:

- 1) First, we describe a symmetric matrix representing the network where each element refer to the Jaccard similarity between nodes (social network users)
- 2) Secondly, we elaborate from this later network an initial solution composed of k sub-detected groups which will be considered as the starting point of our hybrid hierarchical clustering. It consists in beginning with either the agglomerative or the divisive process.
- 3) Then, at each hierarchical level, we elaborate the Average Jaccard Similarity Matrix (*AJSM*) between the sub-detected groups. At each Aggregation Hierarchical level (*AHL*), we merge, from the two groups having the highest average jaccard similarity value, the most similar users. In fact, we refer to the matrix describing the network to determine users having the highest jaccard similarity value.

In the same way, at each Decomposition Hierarchical level (*DHL*), we decompose, from the two groups having the least average jaccard similarity value, the less similar users.

As mentioned in Fig. 1, we weigh every edge by the value of Jaccard similarity defined in (1). First of all, we model the undirected graph as symmetric matrix which summarizes jaccard similarity value between users. In this graph, $JSS_{u_i, u_j} = JSS_{u_j, u_i}$. Thus, we present this general *JSS* matrix:

Fig. 1 Example of Network

$$\begin{pmatrix}
 & u_1 & u_2 & u_3 & u_4 & u_5 & u_6 \\
 u_1 & 0 & 0.67 & 0.58 & 0.87 & 0.76 & 0.84 \\
 u_2 & - & 0 & 0 & 0.17 & 0.46 & 0.55 \\
 u_3 & - & - & 0 & 0.03 & 0.66 & 0.28 \\
 u_4 & - & - & - & 0 & 0.33 & 0.59 \\
 u_5 & - & - & - & - & 0 & 0.08 \\
 u_6 & - & - & - & - & - & 0
 \end{pmatrix}$$

Then, the next step consists in determining an initial solution defined by using only the agglomerative algorithm. As depicted in Fig. 2, the initial solution is composed of three sub-detected groups namely $C = \{\{u_1, u_2\}\} + \{\{u_3, u_4\}\} + \{\{u_5, u_6\}\}$.

Fig. 2 Initial Solution of HHCCD

Furthermore, at each level (AHL or DHL), we compute *MoySim* matrix based on the average similarity between the sub-detected groups. We obtain this similarity:

$$MoySim(c_k) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n JSS_{u_i, u_j}}{\sum_{j=1}^n V_j} \quad (2)$$

Consequently, *MoySim* matrix of the initial solution can be defined by:

$$\begin{pmatrix}
 & \{u_1, u_2\} & \{u_3, u_4\} & \{u_5, u_6\} \\
 \{u_1, u_2\} & 0 & \mathbf{0.405} & 0.652 \\
 \{u_3, u_4\} & - & 0 & 0.465 \\
 \{u_5, u_6\} & - & - & 0
 \end{pmatrix}$$

It is injected as input to the proposed hybrid hierarchical clustering process starting either by the aggregation or the decomposition operator.

First Case: HHCCDA starting with the decomposition operator R2:

HDL1: Referring to *MoySim* matrix of the initial solution, we note that, the two groups $\{u_1, u_2\}$ and $\{u_3, u_4\}$ have less important *JSS* value than other groups. For this reasons, we decompose, from these groups, user having the least similarity value then others by referring to the general *JSS* matrix. In this case, as u_3 has the smallest similarity value, it will be separated from the sub-detected groups. Consequently, after the application of R2, the generated *JSS* matrix becomes:

$$\begin{pmatrix}
 & \{u_1, u_2\} & \{u_3\} & \{u_4\} & \{u_5, u_6\} \\
 \{u_1, u_2\} & 0 & 0.19 & 0.34 & 0.61 \\
 \{u_3\} & - & 0 & 0.015 & 0.31 \\
 \{u_4\} & - & - & 0 & 0.3 \\
 \{u_5, u_6\} & - & - & - & 0
 \end{pmatrix}$$

HAL1: At this step, based on this later *MoySim* matrix we apply R1 algorithm. In fact, we notice that the two sub-detected groups $\{u_1, u_2\}$ and $\{u_5, u_6\}$ have the highest average similarity value. Hence, we merge them to form the same sub-detected group. Consequently, generated *MoySim* matrix becomes:

$$\begin{pmatrix}
 & \{u_1, u_2, u_5, u_6\} & \{u_3\} & \{u_4\} \\
 \{u_1, u_2, u_5, u_6\} & 0 & 0.3 & 0.39 \\
 \{u_3\} & - & 0 & 0.015 \\
 \{u_4\} & - & - & 0
 \end{pmatrix}$$

HDL2: Obviously, users 3 and 4 are already separated. Therefore, at this level, we omit from the group $\{u_1, u_2, u_5, u_6\}$ user having the least similarity value with u_3 . Thus, we isolate u_5 from the later group as it has the least *JSS* value. We present the generated *MoySim* matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix}
 & \{u_1, u_2, u_6\} & \{u_3\} & \{u_4\} & \{u_5\} \\
 \{u_1, u_2, u_6\} & 0 & 0.215 & 0.407 & 0.325 \\
 \{u_3\} & - & 0 & 0.015 & 0.33 \\
 \{u_4\} & - & - & 0 & 0.165 \\
 \{u_5\} & - & - & - & 0
 \end{pmatrix}$$

HAL2: We notice that u_5 has the most important average similarity value. So, we integrate it into the sub-detected group $\{u_1, u_2, u_6\}$. Thus, applying R1, the generated *MoySim* matrix becomes:

$$\begin{pmatrix}
 & \{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\} & \{u_3\} & \{u_5\} \\
 \{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\} & 0 & 0.178 & 0.326 \\
 \{u_3\} & - & 0 & 0.33 \\
 \{u_5\} & - & - & 0
 \end{pmatrix}$$

HDL3: At this level, we show that the two sub-detected groups $\{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\}$ and $\{u_3\}$ have the smallest average similarity value. For this reason, we decompose from the group $\{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\}$, user having the less important *JSS* with u_3 . In this case, u_2 is the concerned by the decomposition. Thus, the generated *MoySim* matrix becomes:

$$\begin{pmatrix}
 & \{u_1, u_4, u_6\} & \{u_2\} & \{u_3\} & \{u_5\} \\
 \{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\} & 0 & 0.347 & 0.222 & 0.292 \\
 \{u_2\} & - & 0 & 0 & 0.23 \\
 \{u_3\} & - & - & 0 & 0.33 \\
 \{u_5\} & - & - & - & 0
 \end{pmatrix}$$

HAL3: At this level, two sub-detected groups $\{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\}$ and $\{u_2\}$, having the highest average similarity value, are merged. We define the generated *MoySim* matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} & \{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\} & \{u_3\} & \{u_5\} \\ \{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\} & 0 & 0.178 & 0.326 \\ \{u_3\} & - & 0 & 0.33 \\ \{u_5\} & - & - & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

HDL4: At this step, we notice that, if we apply R2, we separate u_2 from the two sub-detected groups $\{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\}$ and $\{u_3\}$ having the smallest average similarity. Thus, the solution remains constant and we obtained the same sub-detected group of *HDL3* level. Consequently, the three detected groups are $\{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\}$, $\{u_3\}$ and $\{u_5\}$. For this reason, the process of R1 or R2 stops at this solution.

Second Case: HHCCDA Starting by the Aggregation Operator R1:

HAL1: Our starting point is always the *MoySim* matrix of the initial solution. Furthermore, we are interested in merging the two sub-detected groups $\{u_1, u_2\}$ and $\{u_5, u_6\}$ because they have the highest average Jaccard similarity value. Thus, after applying the aggregation algorithm R1, the generated *MoySim* matrix becomes:

$$\begin{pmatrix} & \{u_1, u_2, u_5, u_6\} & \{u_3, u_4\} \\ \{u_1, u_2, u_5, u_6\} & 0 & 0.58 \\ \{u_3, u_4\} & - & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

HDL1: At this level, we apply the decomposition operator to decompose, from the two sub-detected groups $\{u_1, u_2, u_5, u_6\}$ and $\{u_3, u_4\}$, users having the least important *JSS*. In this case, users u_3 and u_4 form a separated group. Thus, the generated *MoySim* matrix :

$$\begin{pmatrix} & \{u_1, u_2, u_5, u_6\} & \{u_3\} & \{u_4\} \\ \{u_1, u_2, u_5, u_6\} & 0 & 0.304 & 0.392 \\ \{u_3\} & - & 0 & 0.015 \\ \{u_4\} & - & - & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

HAL2 : At this level, we merge the two sub-detected groups $\{u_1, u_2, u_5, u_6\}$ and $\{u_4\}$ having the highest average similarity value. Consequently, the generated *MoySim* matrix becomes:

$$\begin{pmatrix} & \{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_5, u_6\} & \{u_3\} \\ \{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_5, u_6\} & 0 & 0.258 \\ \{u_3\} & - & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

HDL2: In the same way, we decompose from the sub-detected group $\{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_5, u_6\}$ user having the lowest *JSS* with $\{m_3\}$.

Therefore, the generated *MoySim* matrix becomes:

$$\begin{pmatrix} & \{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\} & \{u_3\} & \{u_5\} \\ \{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\} & 0 & 0.178 & 0.326 \\ \{u_3\} & - & 0 & 0.033 \\ \{u_5\} & - & - & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

HAL3 : At this level, the two sub-detected groups $\{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\}$ and $\{u_5\}$ having the highest average similarity value are merged. We present the generated

MoySim matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} & \{u_1, u_2, u_5, u_6\} & \{u_3\} & \{u_4\} \\ \{u_1, u_2, u_5, u_6\} & 0 & 0.304 & 0.392 \\ \{u_3\} & - & 0 & 0.015 \\ \{u_4\} & - & - & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

HDL3: At this level, we notice that, by applying R1, we merge the two sub-detected groups $\{u_1, u_2, u_5, u_6\}$ and $\{u_4\}$ having the highest average similarity value. Thus, the solution remains constant and we obtain the same sub-detected group of level *HAL2*. As the result of the first case, the three detected communities are $\{u_1, u_2, u_4, u_6\}$, $\{u_3\}$ and $\{u_5\}$. We note the end of the R2 or R1 process at this stable solution.

Particularly in this example, we notice that we obtain the same stable partitions starting either with the aggregation or the decomposition operator. However, the obtained partitions are not necessarily the same.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

We conducted series of experiments to evaluate the proposed hybrid hierarchical clustering for community detection on both real and artificial networks in order to obtain accurate and decisive results.

CoreCluster Algorithm: We choose to compare our hybrid clustering algorithm with CORECLUSTER framework because both algorithms focus on processing the graph in a hierarchical manner. We used the Christos, Fragkiskos Dimitrios and Michalis CoreCluster algorithm as it is described in [22]. In fact, this algorithm is an efficient graph clustering framework based on the concept of graph degeneracy. Referring to the k-core decomposition, this algorithm focuses on the hierarchical organization of the sub-detected groups of the graph. Indeed, the k-core decomposition was used to prove the cohesion of social networks. Hence, it has been applied in several graph-related tasks, such as graph visualization [24], as an edge ordering criterion for graph coarsening [25], as well as in the decomposition of massive graphs [23].

A. Evaluation on Artificial Networks

We exploited hierarchical benchmark to test our method. In fact, we used a benchmark which is a simple extension of Girvan and Newman benchmark [26] and Arenas et al benchmark [27]. This benchmark contains 512 nodes arranged into 16 groups divided into four sub-detected partitions in which each node has an average of k_i links ($i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$). K_1 denotes the average link with the 31 related partitions of its group. The interactions between 96 nodes of the remaining three groups and the group of K_1 link are represented by the average of k_2, k_3 represent, for each node, the number of ties with the rest of the network and the degree of mixing of the four groups. In fact, these various average links lead to the emergence of two different hierarchical levels: lower hierarchical level representing micro-communities, containing 128 groups, and higher hierarchical one composed of macro-communities made up of 16 small groups.

To evaluate the efficiency of our method on this hierarchical benchmark, we used the Normalized Mutual Information NMI to compare the computed partitions and the exact partitions of the network at each level. In fact, the NMI is obtained by this equation [22]:

$$NMI(A, B) = \frac{-2 \sum_{a \in A} \sum_{b \in B} |a \cap b| \log\left(\frac{|a \cap b| n}{|a| |b|}\right)}{\sum_{a \in A} |a| \log\left(\frac{|a|}{n}\right) + \sum_{b \in B} |b| \log\left(\frac{|b|}{n}\right)} \quad (3)$$

where A is the real partitions of the network and B represents the partition obtained by the used algorithm. In fact, $NMI(A, B) = 1$ when both partitions A and B coincide and higher values are better.

In Fig. 3, we compare the performance of the CoreCluster with that of our algorithm for different hierarchical levels and various mixing parameter (k_3) values.

At the lower level, the community contains 16 clusters; each of which is made up of 32 nodes. As indicated in Fig. 3 (b), the proposed method in its two cases (agglomerative or divisive) is efficiently used considering that each node has as many links inside as outside each micro-community, for any value of k_3 . Besides, we notice that, in micro-communities, our approach performs almost perfectly (with $NMI > 0.85$ and $k_3 < 30$) and generally outperforms the quality of the CoreCluster algorithm in most cases, especially as the mixing parameters grows. Moving on to the comparison of our method in its both cases, we see that divisive $HHCCDA$ displays better clustering quality than the agglomerative $HHCCDA$ and the difference is negligible. Overall, for the micro-communities, the provided findings are so important. Partitions are always well mixed with each other. For example, when our algorithm starts, with the aggregation operator (agglomerative $HHCCDA$), $NMI = 0.89$ and $K_3 = 30$. Starting with decomposition operator (Divisive $HHCCDA$), $NMI = 0.95$ and $K_3 = 30$. However, the performance of CoreCluster algorithm is considerably lower than that of the proposed algorithm.

At the higher level (Fig. 3 (b)), the communities contains four clusters; each of which includes 32 nodes, for with a total of 128 nodes per cluster. Obviously, our algorithm displays better clustering quality than CoreCluster, with the exception of ($15 < k_3 < 25$). Obviously, detection of groups in macro-communities is correctly identified for $k_3 < 25$. However, the drawback of results appears only when $k_3 \sim 35$. Generally, in both hierarchical levels, we obtain good results.

B. Evaluation on Real Networks

We also performed evaluations on a real networks. Thus, we used the 140dev Twitter framework [28]. The data set were collected by crawling two weeks of public tweets from the 1st till the 15th of January 2016. We built a weighted graph with the coefficient of jaccard defined in (1) modeling the networks. Additionally, we evaluated our results using the evaluation criterion of conductance whose measures (for a

cluster) present the ratio of internal to external connectivity. Conductance criterion has been used widely to examine clustering quality [29]. Indeed, conductance has values in the range (0, 1) with lower values indicating better clustering quality.

Given a graph G and a cut (S, \bar{S}) , conductance is defined as:

$$\phi(S) = \frac{\sum_{i \in S, j \notin S} A_{i,j}}{\min(a(S), a(\bar{S}))} \quad (4)$$

where A_{ij} are the entries in the adjacency matrix A of G and $a(S) = \sum_{i \in S} \sum_{j \notin S} A_{i,j}$. In Fig. 4, we compare the conductance values versus different sizes of the detected communities obtained using our algorithm with those provided applying CoreCluster. Hence, we notice that $HHCCDA$, in its both cases (agglomerative and divisive), displays better clustering quality than the CoreCluster, especially with medium cluster size ([1500 – 2500]). Besides, when our algorithm starts with using the aggregation operator (agglomerative $HHCCDA$), it outperforms the quality of the divisive $HHCCDA$ and that of CoreCluster, especially when the graph size increases. However, if we have less than 600 nodes, the conductance of divisive $HHCCDA$ is less than 0.3, reflecting a better clustering quality. Overall, our algorithm, in its both cases, displays a quite low conductance regardless of the cluster size.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we are interested in the issue of community detection that can reveal the hierarchy of communities in complex networks. The proposed algorithm integrates three different hierarchical methods that can be used to find clusters in complex networks. The first technique, called ascendant algorithm R1 merged, at each iteration, the two communities having the highest jaccard similarity. The second one method, named descendant hierarchical clustering focused on removing edges having the least similarity. Finally, the hybrid algorithm combined the two previously-mentioned ones. In fact, the proposed hybrid hierarchical algorithm assumed the existence of an initial solution of k detected community. Then, it applied alternatively the aggregation and the decomposition operator. Moreover we described analytically why the proposed algorithm scales-up the clustering process and we showed experimentally that our method improves the clustering quality. However, our algorithm stopped at obtaining a stable locally-optimal solution. In a future work, we will try to integrate an optimization process and find globally optimal detected communities.

(a) Lower Hierarchical level (micro-Communities) : NMI

(b) higher Hierarchical level (Macro-Communities) : NMI

Fig. 3 Comparison of the clustering quality in terms of NMI for artificial network

Fig. 4 Comparison of the clustering quality in terms of conductance (lower values are better) for real network

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